

Metal Complex as Ligand : Binuclear Alkali and Alkaline Earth Metal Complexes with Magnesium Bis-8-hydroxyquinolate

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To study the alkali and alkaline earth metals with due reference to the chances of complex formation, we have selected magnesium bis-8-hydroxyquinolate¹ denoted as Mg(8HQ)₂, as metal complex ligand and studied its behaviour.

The complexes have been synthesised with a view that it may be useful to explain the discriminatory behaviour that exists in nature.

Results and Discussion

The adducts (Table 1) are sparingly soluble in polar solvents but insoluble in non-polar ones. They are stable under dry condition but decompose on exposure to moisture; as such they were kept in a desiccator over anhydrous CaCl₂. Analytical data show that one molecule of alkali metal salt of M_aL (where M = Li, Na, K ; L = deprotonated 1-nitroso-2-naphthol and 8-hydroxyquinoline) combined with one molecule of magnesium oxinate and the general formula of the adducts have been established as M_aL.Mg(8HQ)₂; whereas with alkaline earth metal salts, one molecule of alkaline earth metal salt of M_bX₂ (where M_b = Mg, Ca ; X = Cl, Br) combined with two molecules of Mg(8HQ)₂ and the general formula of the adducts have been established as M_bX₂.{Mg(8HQ)₂}₂.

In the complex ligand, magnesium-bis-8-hydroxyquinolate, bands 1595 and 1335 cm⁻¹ have been assigned for C = N and C = O res-

pectively. In the adducts the C = N frequency shows upward shifts and are observed at 1598-1610 cm⁻¹ and the C = O frequency shows downward shifts at 1332-1325 cm⁻¹.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd. (Colour)	Transition (t) Decomp. (d) temp. (°C)	Analysis%:Found/(Calcd.)	
		Mg	N
Mg(8HQ) ₂ (Yellow)	> 360	7.65 (7.77)	8.28 (8.96)
Mg(8HQ) ₂ .Li8HQ (Yellow)	355t	5.63 (5.25)	8.55 (9.07)
Mg(8HQ) ₂ .Na8HQ (Yellowish green)	300t	5.08 (5.07)	8.77 (8.76)
Mg(8HQ) ₂ .K8HQ (Yellow)	290t	5.05 (4.91)	7.55 (8.48)
Mg(8HQ) ₂ .Na1N2N (Yellowish green)	279d	4.79 (5.43)	8.23 (9.25)
Mg(8HQ) ₂ .K1N2N (Green)	275d	4.64 (4.82)	8.02 (7.91)
{Mg(8HQ) ₂ } ₂ .MgCl ₂ (Yellow)	> 360	9.07 (10.12)	7.83 (7.78)
{Mg(8HQ) ₂ } ₂ .MgBr ₂ (Brown)	> 360	9.24 (9.01)	5.72 (6.92)
{Mg(8HQ) ₂ } ₂ .CaBr ₂ (Yellow)	> 360	5.20 (5.89)	6.81 (6.81)

* 1N2N = 1-nitroso-2-naphthol; 8HQ = 8-hydroxyquinoline.

Complex ligand is a dimer which breaks up during the course of adduct formation. Oxygen atoms which were attached to magnesium atoms are no longer bonded in that form in the adducts, rather most likely weakly-bonded to the alkali and alkaline earth metals.

The upward shifting of $C = N$ frequency is due to localisation of electron. Shyamal and Ghanekar² are also of the opinion that phenolic ν_{C-O} is expected to occur at higher energy in comparison to alcoholic/enolic ν_{C-O} due to electron delocalisation from phenolic $C-O$ towards the benzene ring. The above assignments were also found compatible with those made for the $C = O$ and $C = N$ links in alkali and alkaline earth metal adducts with $Ni(8HQ)_2$ and $Cu(8HQ)_2$.

Proposed structures of the adducts have been shown in Figs. 1a and 1b.

$M_a = Li, Na, K$; $L = IN_2N, 8HQ$.
Fig. 1a

Experimental

The usual method of synthesis was to add $Mg(8HQ)_2$ in the saturated solutions of alkali

$M_b = Mg, Ca$; $X = Cl, Br$.
Fig. 1b

and alkaline earth metal salts in absolute ethanol roughly in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratio respectively. The reaction mixture was refluxed with constant stirring on a hot plate for 4–5 h at 80° . The mixture was then allowed to cool in a desiccator over anhydrous $CaCl_2$, filtered, washed thoroughly with absolute ethanol and dried in an air-oven at 80° for 3 h to yield the product.

References

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